

Misleading findings in Dresen's review (2023) on vitamin C for critical illness

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The authors have not responded to the PubPeer critique by 2026.

See a parallel description of flaws in another report

by Hill A, Stoppe C, et al. (2019)

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32102297>

<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12020586>

<https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6643/12/2/586/s1> Detailed description of the errors

<https://zenodo.org/records/19733780> Detailed description of the errors

See a parallel description of flaws in another report

by Stoppe C, Hill A, et al. (2019)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19855543>

See a parallel description of flaws in another report

by Hill A, Stoppe C, et al. (2018)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19789077>

Comment on:

Dresen E, Lee ZY, Hill A, Notz Q, Patel JJ, Stoppe C.

History of scurvy and use of vitamin C in critical illness: a narrative review.

Nutr Clin Pract. 2023;38(1):46-54.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36156315>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/ncp.10914>

Dresen's references are listed here with bold numbers, so that **16** indicates Dresen reference number 16. The additional references in this comment use letters added to the Dresen reference number so that they indicate comments related to the particular Dresen reference, eg, reference 16a challenges the validity of Dresen reference **16**. Instead of renumbering the Dresen references, this approach helps to associate the references with the text section of Dresen.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

Dresen et al write [p.48]: “Clinically manifested scurvy goes along with vitamin C serum concentrations of $\leq 10 \mu\text{mol/L}$ ”

There are no references given to support this statement.

Scurvy is often associated with vitamin C levels below 0.2 mg/dl [11 $\mu\text{mol/L}$]. However, 11 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ should not be interpreted as a definitive level below which scurvy symptoms start to appear. For example, Hodges commented in their report of the most recent empirical scurvy trial that

“a distressing feature is the lack of precision of serum ascorbic acid levels. According to most authorities, deficiency appears after the serum level has fallen below 0.2 mg/100 ml, yet several men in these studies had obvious scurvy at a time when their serum levels were above this value” [13a].

In that study, the emergence of scurvy symptoms had a much closer correlation with the total body pool of vitamin C than with plasma vitamin C level. Hodges further stated that *“... a comparison between plasma levels of ascorbate and pool sizes showed a very poor correlation... it is fair to say that scurvy appeared when the [vitamin C] body pool size fell below 300 mg”* [13b]. Thus, $\leq 10 \mu\text{mol/L}$ is a poor measure for considering whether a person suffers from scurvy or not.

Furthermore, 5% of people examined in the USA had vitamin C level below 8 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ [13c]. However, it is not reasonable to state that 1 in 20 people in the USA suffer from clinically manifested scurvy.

13a. Hodges RE. What’s new about scurvy? Am J Clin Nutr. 1971;24(4):383-4.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/5090622>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/24.4.383>

13b. Hodges RE, Hood J, Canham JE, Sauberlich HE, Baker EM. Clinical manifestations of ascorbic acid deficiency in man. Am J Clin Nutr. 1971;24(4):432-43.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/5090631>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/24.4.432>

13c. Schleicher RL, Carroll MD, Ford ES, Lacher DA. Serum vitamin C and the prevalence of vitamin C deficiency in the United States: 2003-2004 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES).

Am J Clin Nutr. 2009;90(5):1252-63.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19675106>

<https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.2008.27016>

Dresen et al write [p.48]: “vitamin C may affect the functionality of various organs and systems, such as heart, lung, kidneys, brain, blood, and immune defense (Figure 2), which may be impaired during low vitamin C levels and critical illness [16]”

Dresen et al write [p.51]: “Examples in which benefits of vitamin C administration have been shown ... are ... after organ surgery requiring to temporarily clamp large arteries [16]”

Dresen’s reference 16 has a number of severe errors [16a].

16. Hill A, Wendt S, Benstoem C, Neubauer C, Meybohm P, Langlois P, Adhikari NK, Heyland DK, Stoppe C. Vitamin C to improve organ dysfunction in cardiac surgery patients – Review and pragmatic approach. *Nutrients*. 2018;10(8):974.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30060468>

<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu10080974>

16a. Hemilä H. Misleading review on vitamin C and cardiac patients by Hill et al. (2018). *PubPeer* 2019.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19789076>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/DEBED5D9F498A0C940E18841C25C75#1>

Dresen et al write [p.49]: “Low vitamin C status at intensive care unit (ICU) admission ... In this context, enteral supplementation of vitamin C is ineffective in restoring plasma concentration to normal levels due to the saturable intestinal uptake via the SVCT1 [21]”

Reference 21 reports that 2.5 grams/day enteral vitamin C increases plasma vitamin C level to 80 µmol/L; such a finding does not support the above statement. Furthermore, a meta-analysis comparing the effects of enteral vs intravenous vitamin C administration on the duration of ICU stay found no difference between the two routes of administration [21a: Table 2]. This comparison should not be ignored when considering the use of vitamin C for ICU patients. Oral administration is much less costly for patients who are able to take tablets.

21. Levine M, et al. Vitamin C pharmacokinetics in healthy volunteers.

Proc Natl Acad Sci USA. 1996;93(8):3704-9.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8623000>

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.93.8.3704>

21a. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C can shorten the length of stay in the ICU:

A meta-analysis. *Nutrients*. 2019;11(4):708.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30934660>

<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11040708>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6521194>

Dresen et al write [p.50]: “For vitamin C monotherapy, the beneficial effect was further strengthened by the CITRIS-ALI trial, a multicenter trial among 170 patients with sepsis and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) who were administered IV vitamin C at 50 mg/kg every 6 h for up to 96 h vs placebo [42]”

Reference 42 was re-analyzed and a statistically significant difference between the trial groups was shown between the 4-day period of vitamin C administration and the period after vitamin C administration [42a,42b]. This finding should not be ignored when considering the CITRIS-ALI trial.

Comment [42b] on the CITRIS-ALI trial was published 3 years before Dresen’s (2023) paper and was available at PubMed.

42. Fowler AA, et al. Effect of vitamin C infusion on organ failure and biomarkers of inflammation and vascular injury in patients with sepsis and severe acute respiratory failure: The CITRIS-ALI randomized clinical trial. JAMA. 2019;322(13):1261-1270.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31573637>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2019.11825>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6777268>

42a. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Reanalysis of the effect of vitamin C on mortality in the CITRIS-ALI trial: Important findings dismissed in the trial report. Front Med. 2020;7:590853.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33117837>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.590853>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7575729>

42b. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine: Examples from trials of vitamin C for infections. Life. 2022;12(1):62.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455>

<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8779885>

Dresen et al write [p.51]: “the most recent landmark trial (the LOVIT trial) on IV vitamin C monotherapy found results, which were in apparent contrast to previous findings [43]”

Reference 43 was also re-analyzed and again a statistically significant difference between the trial groups was shown between the 4-day period of vitamin C administration and the period after vitamin C administration [43a,43b]. This should not be ignored when considering the LOVIT findings. The modification of mortality by abruptly stopping vitamin C was not “*in apparent contrast to previous findings*” because the same phenomenon was observed in the CITRIS-ALI trial [42a].

43. Lamontagne F, et al. Intravenous vitamin C in adults with sepsis in the intensive care unit.

N Engl J Med. 2022;386(25):2387-2398.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35704292>

<https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2200644>

43a. Hemilä H. Abrupt termination of vitamin C may explain excess mortality in the LOVIT trial. PubPeer 2022 July.

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/5239511630C295A0EB163A1AC0D212#1>

43b. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Abrupt termination of vitamin C from ICU patients may increase mortality: secondary analysis of the LOVIT trial. Eur J Clin Nutr. 2023;77(4):490-494.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36539454>

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41430-022-01254-8>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10115628>

Dresen et al write [p.51]: “ambulatory outpatients with COVID-19 did not benefit from vitamin C supplementation with regards to the duration of symptoms [55]”

The original statistical analysis of the COVID A to Z trial [55] was flawed in that censored patients were imputed as cured at the end of the follow-up. Statistically appropriate analyses using Cox regression [55a] and quantile treatment effects [55b: Fig 4] indicate that there was benefit from vitamin C supplementation.

Comment [55a] on the COVID A to Z trial was published 2 years before Dresen’s (2023) paper and was available at PubMed.

55. Thomas S, et al. Effect of high-dose zinc and ascorbic acid supplementation vs usual care on symptom length and reduction among ambulatory patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection: The COVID A to Z randomized clinical trial. JAMA Netw Open. 2021;4(2):e210369.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33576820>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.0369>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7881357>

55a. Hemilä H, Carr A, Chalker E. Vitamin C may increase the recovery rate of outpatient cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection by 70%: Reanalysis of the COVID A to Z randomized clinical trial. Front Immunol. 2021;12:674681.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34040614>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.674681>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8141621>

55b. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine: Examples from trials of vitamin C for infections. Life. 2022;12(1):62.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455>

<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8779885>

Dresen et al write [p.51]: “Examples in which benefits of vitamin C administration have been shown after I/R-injury are patients undergoing open heart surgery using cardiopulmonary bypass [58-64]”

Reference 58 is a correction of a meta-analysis [58a], which had a large number of errors [59b,59c]. The PubMed abstract of the original paper still contains the errors [58a], while the PubMed record for the correction does not include any abstract [58]. Therefore readers are probably confused about the findings of the meta-analysis.

58. Hill A, Clasen KC, Wendt S, Majoros ÁG, Stoppe C, Adhikari NK, Heyland DK, Benstoem C. Correction: Hill, A.; et al. Effects of vitamin C on organ function in cardiac surgery patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutrients* 2019, 11, 2103. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(12):3910. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33371532> The abstract still has all the errors described in [58b,58c] <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12123910> <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7767510>

58a. Hill A, Clasen KC, Wendt S, Majoros ÁG, Stoppe C, Adhikari NKJ, Heyland DK, Benstoem C. Effects of vitamin C on organ function in cardiac surgery patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutrients*. 2019;11(9):2103. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31487905> <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11092103> <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6769534>

58b. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for cardiac surgery patients: Several errors in a published meta-analysis. Comment on “*Effects of vitamin C on organ function in cardiac surgery patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. Nutrients* 2019, 11, 2103”. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(2):586. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32102297> <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12020586> <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7071442>

58c. Supplementary file of ref. 58b separately. Shows the errors in great detail, whereas the main text of ref. 58b is a short summary of the errors. <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6643/12/2/586/s1> <https://zenodo.org/records/19733780>

[refs. 58-64]: Dresen’s reference 59 also has a number of errors [59a]. For example, in their Fig. 4, Hu et al stated [59] that the standard deviation (SD) of the mean duration of ICU stay in the vitamin C group was 24.9 hours in the trial by Colby et al. However, Colby reported in Table 1 and the text that the SD for the duration of ICU stay was 249.9 hours in their vitamin C group, i.e. 10 times greater than Hu claimed. Such a large error leads to a substantial error in the pooled estimate of effect, but also exaggerates the heterogeneity between the included trials.

Comment [59a] on the Hu (2017) meta-analysis was published 4 years before Dresen’s (2023) paper and was available at PubMed.

59. Hu X, Yuan L, Wang H, Li C, Cai J, Hu Y, Ma C. Efficacy and safety of vitamin C for atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery: A meta-analysis with trial sequential analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Int J Surg*. 2017;37:58-64.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27956113>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2016.12.009>

59a. Hemilä H. Errors in a meta-analysis on vitamin C and post-operative atrial fibrillation.

Int J Surg. 2019;64:66.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30831247>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2019.01.025>

[refs. 58-64]: Dresen's reference 62 also has a number of errors [62a]. In reference 62, the results of 2 rather large randomized controlled trials (RCTs) conducted in the USA were missing from the meta-analysis. The authors [62] also stated that “*only RCTs that compared ascorbic acid with a placebo or other control were included*” in their review, but they included a study which was not an RCT [62a].

Comment [62a] on the Baker (2017) meta-analysis was published 6 years before Dresen's (2023) paper and was available at PubMed.

62. Baker WL, Coleman CI. Meta-analysis of ascorbic acid for prevention of postoperative atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery. *Am J Health Syst Pharm*. 2016;73(24):2056-2066.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27806938>

<https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp160066>

62a. Hemilä H. Publication bias in meta-analysis of ascorbic acid for postoperative atrial fibrillation.

Am J Health Syst Pharm. 2017;74(6):372-373.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28274978>

<https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp160999>

<https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/312602>

Dresen et al write [p.51-52]: “Patients experiencing chronic oxidative stress causing organ damage are suggested to benefit from vitamin C as well, for example, in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease [68,69]”

Reference 68 is not a “vitamin C” trial though the above sentence implies so. It is a “vitamin C + vitamin E” trial. Dresen et al do not provide a supporting argument for the assumption that vitamin E is inactive in the context of a controlled trial on vitamin C. Conversely, there is much empirical evidence indicating that vitamin C and vitamin E can interact in vitro and in vivo [68a-68k], which means that findings from a “vitamin C + vitamin E” trial should not be attributed to vitamin C alone.

68. Nathens AB, et al. Randomized, prospective trial of antioxidant supplementation in critically ill surgical patients. *Ann Surg*. 2002;236(6):814-22.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12454520>

<https://doi.org/10.1097/00000658-200212000-00014>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1422648>

- 68a. Hemilä H, Kaprio J. Modification of the effect of vitamin E supplementation on the mortality of male smokers by age and dietary vitamin C. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2009;169:946-53.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwn413>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2661323>
- 68b. Bruno RS, et al. Faster plasma vitamin E disappearance in smokers is normalized by vitamin C supplementation. *Free Radic Biol Med.* 2006;40(4):689-97.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16458200>
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2005.10.051>
- 68c. Bruno RS, Ramakrishnan R, Montine TJ, Bray TM, Traber MG. α -Tocopherol disappearance is faster in cigarette smokers and is inversely related to their ascorbic acid status. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2005;81(1):95-103.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15640466>
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/81.1.95>
- 68d. Hamilton IM, et al. Interactions between vitamins C and E in human subjects. *Br J Nutr.* 2000;84(3):261-7.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10967604>
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0007114500001537>
- 68e. Liu JF, Lee YW. Vitamin C supplementation restores the impaired vitamin E status of guinea pigs fed oxidized frying oil. *J Nutr.* 1998;128(1):116-22.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9430612>
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/128.1.116>
- 68f. May JM, Qu ZC, Mendiratta S. Protection and recycling of alpha-tocopherol in human erythrocytes by intracellular ascorbic acid. *Arch Biochem Biophys.* 1998;349(2):281-9.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9448716>
<https://doi.org/10.1006/abbi.1997.0473>
- 68g. Tanaka K, et al. Interactions between vitamin C and vitamin E are observed in tissues of inherently scorbutic rats. *J Nutr.* 1997;127(10):2060-4.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9311965>
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/127.10.2060>
- 68h. Wijesundara MBJ, Berger S. The redox pair vitamin E and vitamin C, a ^{13}C -NMR Study. *Liebigs Annalen der Chemie.* 1994;(12):1239-41.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jlac.199419941216>
- 68i. Sharma MK, Buettner GR. Interaction of vitamin C and vitamin E during free radical stress in plasma: an ESR study. *Free Radic Biol Med.* 1993;14(6):649-53.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8392021>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0891-5849\(93\)90146-l](https://doi.org/10.1016/0891-5849(93)90146-l)
- 68j. Bendich A, D'Apolito P, Gabriel E, Machlin LJ. Interaction of dietary vitamin C and vitamin E on guinea pig immune responses to mitogens. *J Nutr.* 1984;114(9):1588-93.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/6332184>
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/114.9.1588>
- 68k. Packer JE, Slater TF, Willson RL. Direct observation of a free radical interaction between vitamin E and vitamin C. *Nature.* 1979;278(5706):737-8.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/431730>
<https://doi.org/10.1038/278737a0>

Dresen et al write [p.47]: *“In 1747, the Scottish surgeon James Lind was interested in scurvy ... He randomized 12 seamen with scurvy, two at a time, to six dietary interventions and found oranges and lemons produced the most sudden and visible effect ... Unfortunately, the idea of dietary cause of scurvy did not gain traction and it was not until 1794 that the British Admiralty allowed Lind to repeat his experiment—this time on an entire fleet of ships. The results in favor of vitamin C were so dramatic that in 1795, the Admiralty made lemon juice a required part of the standard diet of British seamen and scurvy disappeared [1,2]”*

This description of history is misleading. Fruit was reported to be beneficial for scurvy two centuries before Lind [2a-2d], so the idea that there was a dietary cause of scurvy was not Lind's.

Lind's *“experiment occupies only four out of 400 pages of his treatise on scurvy, in several chapters of which he disregards the observations. Scurvy, Lind writes, is provoked mainly by dampness. Adding, in the chapter on prevention, that those affected need dry air. Lind recommends lemon juice only to fight the effects of the dampness inevitable at sea ... To credit Lind with the discovery of lemon juice as a treatment against scurvy therefore seems erroneous”* [2e].

Dresen et al write that Lind *“randomized 12 seamen with scurvy”*, but there is no evidence that Lind randomized the participants. *“Lind does not provide any information on how he allocated the sailors”* [2f], except that Lind wrote that *“Two of the worst patients, with the tendons in the ham rigid, (a symptom none of the rest had), were put under a course of seawater”* [2g-2i], which means that the comparison was biased by design.

It is not clear which studies Dresen et al are referring to when stating that *“it was not until 1794 that the British Admiralty allowed Lind to repeat his experiment”*, as Lind died in 1794 [2c,2d,2j,2k].

Aware of the storage problems for adequate amounts of fresh fruit or fruit-juice during long cruises, Lind recommended that a condensate (called 'rob') be prepared by evaporating a dilution of fresh fruit juice in nearly boiling water over several hours. However, given our current understanding of the properties of vitamin C, it is obvious that there was no anti-scurvy activity in Lind's 'rob'. It is unsurprising that subsequent observers were unable to detect any beneficial effect of the preparation [2d,2i-2k]. Baron concluded that Lind's *“failure to persuade the navy to adopt his rob must have been primarily due to its unimpressive efficacy at sea, presumably because he had boiled this juice”* [2d].

Milne noted that *“there is little evidence, however, that Lind ever clearly recommended the use of lemon juice to the Admiralty or to others”* [2j]. Thus, Lind did not promote *“the idea of dietary cause of scurvy”*.

A further puzzling finding is that Sutton showed that *“if the Navy's own records were taken at face value, Lind never cured scurvy on the Salisbury because there was no sickness there for him to treat”* [2l].

Bartholomew noted that “*we arrange the past into a parade of heroes*” as the factual history shows that “*Lind conceived of scurvy not as a disease of dietary deficiency, but of faulty digestion*” [2m], and “*Scurvy is, he [Lind] says essentially a disease of faulty digestion and excretion*” [2m,2n].

In Carpenter’s view, the fascination with Lind’s 4 pages on his experiment is a twentieth century phenomenon [2c, p.53]. Explanations for scurvy that were unrelated to fruit persisted until the early 20th century [2c].

For example, **Elmer McCollum** was one of the most influential researchers in the field of nutrition in the early part of the 20th century [2o]. In 1917 McCollum proposed that scurvy was caused by constipation [2c,2p,2q]:

“It is much more rational to attribute the development of scurvy to some other cause than a deficiency of some protective ‘vitamine’ in the diet” [2p, p.232].

“The experimental data presented in this paper form, however, a conclusive line of evidence which proves that scurvy in the guinea pig is not a deficiency disease in the sense in which Holst, Funk, Hess, and others have regarded it” [2p, p.234].

“Chart 7 offers definite and convincing evidence that scurvy is in reality the sequel to retention of feces in the cecum” [2p, p.235].

“There are in Charts 3 and 7 curves of growth practically as good in the case of individuals on a plain oat and milk diet and the same after being cured of scurvy by petrolatum administration as we have secured from an oat and milk diet supplemented with orange juice” [2p, p.237].

“The observations reported in this paper furnish definite support for the idea that scurvy in the guinea pig is not the result of the deficiency of a specific protective substance” [2p, p.238].

“The significance of this interpretation is far reaching. It removes from the list one of the syndromes (scurvy) which has long been generally accepted as being due to dietary deficiency” [2p, p.239].

“This fact, together with convincing evidence that scurvy is not in reality a deficiency disease in the sense of being caused by a lack of specific protective substance, warrants an attitude of skepticism regarding the validity of the ‘vitamine’ theory of the etiology of such other diseases as pellagra, rickets, etc., which have been attributed to specific dietary deficiency” [2p, p.239-240].

“We are convinced that the guinea-pig suffers from scurvy on a diet of oats and milk because of the constipating character of the diet ... Scurvy in the guinea-pig is the result of the retention of feces” [2q].

Sir Almroth Wright was a highly distinguished immunologist [2r]. Wright argued that scurvy was due to acid intoxication [2c,2s,2t,2u].

Wright stated: “*When I speak of a blood change in scurvy, I have in my mind a very definite picture of that blood change, and nothing in pathology is to my mind more certainly established, than that the essential essence of scurvy is to be found in a diminution of the alkalinity of the blood.*” [2t, p.95].

“*It was only in 1937, when Lewis Holt showed him that if scorbutic guinea-pigs were given pure crystalline ascorbic acid they were cured of experimental scurvy and that this substance could prevent the condition, that Wright capitulated*” [2h,2u].

When top influential academics believed in the early 20th century, that scurvy was caused by constipation or toxicity, it is not appropriate to accuse British Admiralty of the late 18th century for not being convinced by James Lind’s obscure arguments.

There are several informative texts on the confusion and resulting incorrect statements around Lind’s role in showing fruit is useful against scurvy [2b-2f,2h-2n].

Bachstrom (1734) seems to be the first person to propose that there is something special in fruits and vegetables so that scurvy “*is solely owing to a total abstinence from fresh vegetable food, and greens; which is alone the true primary cause of the disease.*” However, James Lind firmly disagreed with such a supposition [2v].

As to the concept of vitamin as we understand currently, Kenneth Carpenter [2x] (2003) wrote that “It is sometimes asked, ‘Who first had the idea of vitamins?’ ”. The best answers to this question seem to be John Elliotson [2y] and George Budd [2z].

James Lind is the most important person in the history of scurvy, but he did not have an idea of dietary cause of scurvy.

2. Lind J. Nutrition classics. A treatise of the scurvy by James Lind, MDCCLIII. Nutr Res. 1983;41(5):155-157.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.1983.tb07177.x> The correct abbreviation of the journal is “Nutr Rev.”
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